

Speed of Matter is less than Speed of Light

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Abstract: This paper discusses the mass of light and matter and also the relationship of light and matter in motion.

Keywords: mass, volume, motion

1. Introduction

Matter with mass and volume is any substance made up of different kinds of particles that occupies physical space and has inertia. Light commonly refers to electromagnetic radiation that does not occupy space, has no mass or volume. Therefore, light is not considered matter.

2. Motion of Light and Matter

The speed of light in vacuum is known to be almost exactly 3×10^8 metres per second. As light has no mass and volume, the speed of light is always more than the speed of matter moving with mass and volume.

3. Conclusion

In this article, the mass of light and matter and also the relationship of light and matter in motion were discussed in detail.

References

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